

Synthesis of Some 1,3,5-Triphenylpyrazolines and 3,5-Diphenyl-cyclohexen-1-ones

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Since the work of Raiford and Peterson¹, several workers² have synthesised 1,3,5-triphenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazolines from chalcones by condensation with phenylhydrazine. In the present work, 2'-hydroxy-5'-acetamino-4-methoxy-, 2'-hydroxy-5'-acetamino-3,4-methylenedioxy-, and 2',3-dihydroxy-5'-acetamino-chalcones³ have been successfully converted into the corresponding 1-phenyl-3-(2-hydroxy-5-acetaminophenyl)-5-(substituted phenyl)- Δ^2 -pyrazolines (I: R=4-methoxyphenyl, 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl, and 3-hydroxyphenyl).

In chalcones, as in other $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones, the β -carbon atom is more activated towards nucleophilic addition because of the conjugated carbonyl group. The chalcones therefore give rise to various addition reactions with compounds containing a reactive methylene group⁴. With ethyl acetoacetate these form intermediate β -addition products, which are cyclised by an internal aldol condensation to yield 6-ethoxycarbonyl-5,3-diphenyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-ones. The alkaline hydrolysis of these carboxylates provides the corresponding 3,5-diphenyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-ones. In the present work, 2'-hydroxy-5'-acetamino-, 2'-hydroxy-5'-acetamino-4-methoxy-, 2'-hydroxy-5'-acetamino-3,4-methylenedioxy- and 2',3-dihydroxy-5'-acetamino-chalcones³ have been successfully converted into 6-ethoxycarbonyl-5-(substituted phenyl)-3-(2-hydroxy-5-acetaminophenyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-ones (II: R₁=CO₂Et; R=phenyl, 4-methoxyphenyl, 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl, 3-hydroxyphenyl) and subsequently into 5-(substituted phenyl)-3-(2-hydroxy-5-acetaminophenyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-ones (II: R₁=-H; R=phenyl, 4-methoxyphenyl, 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl, and 3-hydroxyphenyl).

1. Raiford and Peterson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1936, 1, 544.
2. Dodwadmath and Wheeler, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 2A, 438; King and King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 569.
3. Raval and Shah, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 1408.
4. Knoevenagel, *Annalen*, 1894, 28, 25; Hill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1115; Nadkarni *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 1798.

Procedure.—A mixture of the chalcone (0.5 g.), phenylhydrazine (0.5 g.), and acetic acid (15.0 ml.) was refluxed at 120-30° for 3 hours. The solid separating on dilution in cold was crystallised from ethanol (Table I).

TABLE I

1-Phenyl-3-(2-hydroxy-5-acetaminophenyl)- Δ^2 -pyrazolines (I).

Substituent, 5-R.	Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
4-Methoxyphenyl	Pale yellow needles	195°	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	10.16	10.47
3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl	Brown shining plates	115-106°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	9.80	10.12
3-Hydroxyphenyl	Thick pale yellow needles	140-50°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	10.53	10.85

To a solution of sodium (0.2 g.) in ethanol (30.0 ml) were added the chalcone (0.5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.5g.); the mixture was refluxed at 90° for 2 hours. The solid separating, on dilution and acidification in cold, was crystallised generally from ethanol or chloroform (Table II).

TABLE II

3-(2-Hydroxy-5-acetaminophenyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-ones (II).

Substituents (6-R ₁ and 5-R ₂).	Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
{ R = Ph R ₁ = -CO ₂ Et	Yellow needles	*148-50°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	3.23	3.56
{ R = Ph R ₁ = -H	Yellow-brown needles	182°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N	4.12	4.36
{ R = 4-methoxyphenyl ³ R ₁ = -CO ₂ Et	Yellow plates	160°	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₆ N	2.92	3.31
{ R = 4-methoxyphenyl R ₁ = -H	Light brown plates	152-53°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	3.76	3.99
{ R = 3:4-methylene- dioxypheyl R ₁ = -CO ₂ Et	Shining brown plates	135°	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₇ N	2.99	3.20
{ R = 3:4-methylene- dioxypheyl R ₁ = -H	Thick light yellow plates	155°	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ N	3.51	3.83
{ R = 2-hydroxyphenyl R ₁ = -CO ₂ Et	Pale yellow needles	*150°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₆ N	3.03	3.42
{ R = 3-hydroxyphenyl R ₁ = -H	Small brown needles	180-81°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	3.80	4.15

*With decomposition.

The ester on boiling with aqueous ethanolic sodium hydroxide for 3 hours afforded the corresponding 3,5-diphenyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1 one which was crystallised from ethanol (50%) (Table II).